

Aeroelastic Load Control Program: In-Flight Demonstration of Active Flow Control Technology

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Abstract—The USAF Test Pilot School (TPS) and the Air Force Research Laboratory (AFRL) have partnered with Lockheed Martin and General Electric (GE) Global Research to execute the first flight test using Dual Bimorph Synthetic Jet (DBSJ) actuators in order to demonstrate the effectiveness of active flow control technology. The first phase of the Aeroelastic Load Control (ALC) program demonstrated the use of small, electronically controlled DBSJ actuators to mitigate the effects of turbulent airflow. The USAF TPS flew three missions that were dedicated to evaluating this technology using a unique configuration on a modified F-16 test aircraft. The primary objective of this test was to validate the configuration as an effective active flow control evaluation platform. The initial results of the flight tests showed some effectiveness in reducing dynamic loads from turbulent airflow when employing the DBSJ actuators. Specifically, parameters reflected a reduction in overall sound pressure levels when the jet actuators were operational. Our data also suggested that active flow control technology merits further investigation using our test configuration, which could potentially lead to some new and innovative solutions to turbulent airflow in the aerospace industry.

AFB, California, GE Global Research, Niskayuna, New York, and Lockheed Martin, Aeronautics Division, Fort Worth, Texas. The results of these wind tunnel tests clearly reflected how operating synthetic jet actuators caused a reduction in turbulent airflow generated by an external aircraft store, which are notable through reduced acoustic levels. Unfortunately, the use of wind tunnels can be expensive and schedule prohibitive. The wide range of dynamic pressure required to evaluate this technology restricts our choices to high demand resources (like NASA’s National Test Facility). Therefore, the time required to use these facilities to accomplish the program’s objectives dramatically increases test cost. More importantly, wind tunnels simulate flight conditions that are limited and may not always be representative to the actual flight environment. Therefore, it became increasingly necessary to develop an airborne configuration to expand the research for this technology where tests can also be repeated under various flight conditions.

This paper^{1 2} summarizes how the test team successfully executed the first flight test employing synthetic jet actuators to manipulate turbulent airflow in the wake of an external pod. The test team consisted of members from the staff of the USAF TPS, AFRL, GE Global Research, and Lockheed Martin, with respective backgrounds spanning the fields of flight test and electrical/structural/aerospace engineering. In order to successfully execute the ALC flight tests, the team utilized numerous tools and processes including extensive aircraft instrumentation, telemetry for real-time analysis, parameter analysis software, and commercial-off-the-shelf (COTS) items such as the latest in hand-held personal computers. The tests included a flight profile designed to produce various buffet responses from a modified dummy Low Altitude Navigation and Targeting Infrared for Night (LANTIRN) targeting pod equipped with DBSJ actuators, referred to as the LANTIRN-ALC pod, designed to modify the airflow generated from the pod. The response from this turbulent airflow was measured through an instrumented right ventral fin on the F-16 aircraft. The primary objective was to validate this F-16/LANTIRN configuration, referred to as the ALC configuration, as an

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1. INTRODUCTION

Recent strides in active flow control technology have been the driving force behind the ALC program. Until the summer of 2005, demonstration of the DBSJ actuators was limited to scalable wind tunnel testing performed by AFRL Propulsion Directorate, Edwards Research Site, Edwards

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effective active flow control evaluation platform under various flight conditions. Based on this objective, data suggested that the ALC configuration can adequately demonstrate the effectiveness of these DBSJ actuators when applied against the turbulent airflow created by the LANTIRN-ALC pod. The relative success of the flight tests were coupled with many challenges that were mitigated through creative solutions by test team personnel. Since these tests were the first airborne demonstration of the ALC configuration, numerous hurdles surfaced that became critical issues for our test program; for example, the limitations on aircraft modification and flight envelope restrictions. These issues have since become lessons learned for TPS and the test team, and will be used to shape our ongoing flight tests on the evolution of active flow control technology.

The intent behind publishing the processes and results from the ALC flight tests is to share lessons learned and introduce our test configuration to the aerospace community as an effective tool for evaluating this technology. Furthermore, sharing our initial results from the ALC flight tests may spark interest and discussion within the aerospace community that may help steer future research and development in this area.

2. BACKGROUND

Turbulent/unsteady airflow can initiate many negative effects on aircraft. Many of these effects result in structural fatigue and failure, which in turn shortens the life-cycle of an airframe requiring costly repairs or redesign.

The use of passive solutions such as leading edge extension (LEX) fences, placards, and damping have traditionally been employed to counter unsteady airflow effects, but are often limited to single-point areas within the airframe design. In many cases, turbulent airflow generated from points on an aircraft or external store can limit the aircraft performance envelope unless a solution is implemented. Take, for example, the introduction of the F-16/LANTIRN configuration in the 1980s.

The F-16/LANTIRN configuration was first introduced during the early 1980s. After initial flight testing, the ventral fin aft of the LANTIRN targeting pod began to fail due to the unusually high buffeting airflow particularly at the transonic and lower supersonic conditions (figure 1). After a comprehensive flight test effort, the ventral fin was redesigned to provide needed strength when positioned aft of a pod shape loaded on aircraft station 5R. Therefore, the only approved F-16/LANTIRN configuration required the newly redesigned 'strengthened' ventral fin. This background is only provided for completeness, as our test effort in no way was attempting to solve this specific problem. This configuration provided an ideal, affordable, repeatable test environment for evaluating active solutions for turbulent airflow.

In the case of the ALC flight test, the F-16/LANTIRN configuration allowed the test team to demonstrate/evaluate the effectiveness of DBSJ actuators when applied against turbulent airflow produced from the LANTIRN-ALC pod (figure 2). The LANTIRN-ALC pod included an internal power source that drove the DBSJ actuators in an extension unit aft of the pod. The extension unit contained a total of six DBSJ actuators and added an additional 4 inches to the total length of the pod.

The DBSJ actuators were designed and manufactured by GE Global Research (GE proprietary technology). Each DBSJ actuator was essentially a small 'can' with disks constructed of piezoelectric material, and connected to a 6-mm-diameter orifice on the targeting pod aft extension. A voltage applied to the disks caused a shape deformity resulting in a change within the cavity volume. The periodic change in cavity volume caused flow into or out of the cavity through the orifice, producing a jet-like flow-field. This DBSJ actuator design produced a peak pressure of approximately 90 inches of water (3.25 pounds per square inch) and a peak velocity of approximately 630 feet per second at 125 root mean square (RMS) voltage. Each DBSJ actuator measured approximately 3 inches in diameter and less than ½ an inch thick, and connected to the orifice on the extension can (figure 3).

Figure 1 – F-16 with LANTIRN pod on station 5R; damage to ventral fin from turbulent pod wake

Figure 2 – LANTIRN-ALC Pod

Figure 3 – DBSJ Extension (photo courtesy of GE Global Research)

The concept of using the ALC configuration with the DBSJ system was a direct result from scaled wind tunnel testing performed by AFRL, GE Global Research, and Lockheed Martin. An active flow control system was developed and tested using generic pod configurations. A small-scale demonstration consisted of a pod model 17.36 inches in length with a synthetic jet actuation assembly integrated at the end of the pod. High response pressure transducers and total pressure probes were installed on a rake 17 inches behind the end of the pod. Figure 4 shows RMS pressure values in the flow field behind the pod when the synthetic jet actuators were on (at 900 Hz) and off respectively. Similarly, a full-scale wind tunnel demonstration was also performed using the LANTIRN-ALC pod without the air scoop³ (figure 5). Again, the results showed a reduction in RMS pressure values when the DBSJs were actuated.

**Figure 4 –
Small Scale ALC Wind Tunnel Configuration and
RMS Pressure Values with and without Actuation**

The common themes from the wind tunnel tests were that pod shedding frequency and wake location were controlled, along with a reduction in amplitude of pressure fluctuations. This was achieved through implementing open loop flow control actuation of the DBSJs.

³ The effects from installing the air scoop on the side of the pod cancelled all effectiveness from DBSJ actuation during wind tunnel testing. For our flight test program, the team agreed to include the scoop as an alternative configuration on future flights for further investigation.

MACH 0.5, 6 ACTUATORS, NO SCOOP

**Figure 5 –
Full Scale ALC Wind Tunnel Configuration;
RMS Pressure Values with and without actuation**

The locations of the DBSJ orifices had an impact on the effectiveness for turbulent wake control. The most optimum position was noted at zero degrees, meaning the center of the six DBSJ actuators was aimed directly opposite the wall of the test chamber. Another significant determinant of the effectiveness of wake control was the excitation frequency of the DBSJ actuators. The optimum excitation frequency observed from full scale wind tunnel testing was 830 Hz⁴. As the frequency shifted from the optimum 830 Hz, the effectiveness decreased and the region of higher fluctuating pressures increased. This trend could not be attributed to only frequency since the DBSJ actuator outputs diminished when driven at any frequency other than the optimum 830 Hz. These results provided the required baseline for the design of the ALC flight test configuration.

⁴ The DBSJ actuators were measured with an optimum frequency of 830 Hz, however the peak was narrow band. Therefore, any slight deviation from the optimum frequency would greatly reduce the effectiveness of the DBSJ actuator output. This was taken into consideration during ground testing.

3. FLIGHT TEST CONFIGURATION AND MODIFICATIONS

Aircraft Configuration

When integrated with the F-16 flight vehicle, the system to be evaluated creates an ‘airborne wind tunnel’ planned for repeated use in evaluation of competing and revolutionary active control technologies. Current computational technology is incapable of adequately modeling a synthetic jet actuator when coupled with a realistic environment. The AFRL and USAF TPS collaborated to design an F-16/LANTIRN ALC test configuration (figure 6) that will provide a quick, cost-effective evaluation of these systems throughout a large dynamic pressure range in a real flight environment.

This first phase of the ALC effort evaluated active flow control technology (i.e., DBSJ actuator) operating from the LANTIRN-ALC pod that was used for the AFRL full scale wind tunnel test. A Block 15 F-16 ventral fin was selected to provide maximum sensitivity to the buffet-induced vibrations created by the pod wake. It was instrumented with two accelerometers, one strain gauge bridge, and six dynamic pressure sensors, to provide a comprehensive data collection capability for the test (figure 7). The Block-15 fin (which was not “strengthened” like the later design) limited the overall flight envelope due to its history of in-flight failure, but that was acceptable during this phase.

The LANTIRN-ALC pod was originally a production-representative dummy LANTIRN targeting pod previously used for flight test. The pod weighed 628 pounds, which was approximately 100 pounds heavier than a normal LANTIRN targeting pod. This (like the Block-15 fin) also resulted in limitations for the performance envelope during flight, but did not have a tremendous impact on our test objectives. Also, operational LANTIRN targeting pods normally employed a cooling scoop. Therefore, the LANTIRN-ALC pod was capable of being configured with or without the scoop (figure 8). For the purpose of these initial ALC sorties, the scoop was not included in the configuration but may be used in future sorties to evaluate its overall effect on the pod wake.

Aircraft Modifications

The aircraft carrying the ALC configuration was an Air Force Flight Test Center Coral Phoenix F-16B aircraft. This particular aircraft, USAF serial number 92-453 (A/C 453), was one of three F-16 aircraft recently modified to include a comprehensive data acquisition system (DAS) primarily intended for curriculum use at the TPS. The DAS recorded the instrumented aircraft parameters of A/C 453 in binary format on a 1.8-gigabyte Personal Computer Memory/Card International Association (PCM/CIA) card and transmitted (via L-Band telemetry) these same parameters for real-time

Figure 6 – ALC F-16B Carrying Modified LANTIRN and Instrumented Ventral Fin

Figure 7 – ALC Instrumented Ventral Fin

Figure 8 – ALC LANTIRN Pod with Scoop Unattached

Figure 9 – ALC Aircraft Modifications

observation and analysis in the TPS control room. These parameters provided a complete analytical picture of the aircraft in-flight performance.

The DAS parameters required for the ALC flight test were pressure altitude, Mach number, true airspeed, angle of attack, angle of sideslip, total temperature, IRIG time, right ventral fin pressures, accelerations and strain, and pressure and temperature inside a DBSJ actuator (used for feedback analysis to determine on and off operations of DBSJs). Low sampling rates (less than 200 samples per second) were required for these measurements except for those on the ALC ventral fin, some of which required sampling rates greater than 5,000 samples per second. The air data parameters and DBSJ actuator temperature were recorded from 24 to 145 samples per second; the right ventral fin pressures and accelerations were recorded at 10,417 samples per second; the strain was recorded at 5,208 samples per second.

Further modifications on A/C 453 were required in order to fully integrate the LANTIRN-ALC pod and the ALC-instrumented ventral fin (figure 9). The DBSJ system on the LANTIRN-ALC pod required 28 volts DC which was to be provided by the aircraft nonessential power system. However, the system limited current at 20 amperes, so it was necessary to tap directly to the aircraft 28-volt bus, then add a 25-ampere circuit breaker to power the pod. Aircraft 453 was not designed for flight testing, which became an issue with the amount of space for integrating the proper cables for both the pod and fin. It was necessary to add patch panels in the engine bay and ammunition bay to have configuration flexibility. Also, the modification engineers went above and beyond their normal techniques by penetrating fuel cells in order to run cables; this

Figure 10 – ALC Hand-Held PC (*OQO Model 01*)

technique is rarely done on this type aircraft, but proved to be critical for the success of the modifications.

The DBSJ actuators on the ALC LANTIRN pod were operated from the rear cockpit using a Windows® XP®-based hand-held PC (figure 10). The PC was a key component that allowed the user to run a graphical user interface (GUI) that manipulated the input voltage, excitation frequency, and on/off operations of the DBSJ system. To meet safety of flight requirements, the PC had to be small and portable, with enough battery power to last up to two hours of constant use. The *OQO Model 01*, was the most logical choice, and met expectations when used during sorties. A ball-mount harness was designed to house the PC on the A/C 453 canopy frame in the rear cockpit. In the case of in-flight canopy loss, the PC would safely depart the aircraft without threat to aircrew.

4. SAFETY CONSIDERATIONS

A significant aspect when planning for and executing the ALC flight test was safety. Throughout the planning stages of these sorties, safety of flight issues consistently became some of the biggest hurdles for the program. The most obvious safety concern was that the ALC DBSJ demonstration relied on a configuration that had a history of damaging the F-16 aircraft structure. As mentioned previously, the initial designs of the F-16 right ventral fin would be susceptible to potential failure under certain flight conditions when the aircraft was configured with the LANTIRN targeting pod. Therefore, the theme that guided flight test planning was to avoid flight conditions at which the ALC fin could be damaged or destroyed, without compromising the conditions that would provide meaningful data. The goal in terms of safety for these initial ALC sorties was to convince the test community that the flights should be categorized as ‘low risk’, which would allow TPS students to perform follow-on flight testing with the ALC configuration, and further the research of active flow control technology.

In order to design the flight test envelope, the team considered the particular flight conditions that caused these fins to break. Specifically, the test team referenced data from the General Dynamics/Royal Netherlands Air Force joint test effort, which also investigated the Block 15 F-16 ventral fin phenomena in relation to the LANTIRN pod wake flow during the mid 1990s. Figure 11 shows that the RMS strain on the ventral fin steadily increased as the aircraft approaches the transonic region, and increased dramatically at and around 0.95 Mach number, illustrating dynamic pressure dependence of this phenomenon. Also, the RMS strain values usually increased at lower altitudes during transonic flight. The vibratory stress levels on these fins over an undetermined amount of time would eventually lead to fin failure and possible loss of fin, and/or cracking of the panel connected to the fin.

Another safety concern was that the modifications to our LANTIRN-ALC pod resulted in a shift in center of gravity, along with an additional 100 lbs added to the overall weight of the pod, which limited the team from referencing the guidelines for uploading the normal operational LANTIRN pod. The modification to an external store needed to be assessed and evaluated by an outside agency that specializes in aircraft store testing. The SEEK EAGLE office, Eglin AFB, Florida, partnered with the test team to evaluate the safety aspects of flying the LANTIRN-ALC pod used for this testing. The SEEK EAGLE office granted a flight clearance that allowed carriage of the LANTIRN-ALC pod on the aircraft as long as 0.95 Mach number was not exceeded, with normal accelerations not to exceed +5 g and -2 g. The combination of the SEEK EAGLE flight clearance along with data from the previous flight testing on the Block 15 ventral fin prompted the test team to develop a test plan

and safety plan that allowed us to gather meaningful data while maintaining our flight envelope limitations.

A significant aspect of the safety plan was the threat hazard analysis (THA) of the potential ALC ventral fin failure. The THA was a part of the formal safety process that allowed the team to identify hazards, along with the steps we would take to mitigate the threat. Specific causes of the fin failure would be structural fatigue along with a loose forward attachment bolt that connected the fin to the aircraft panel.

Figure 11 – Mach Number vs. Strain on Ventral Fin (Dutch Flight Test Data)

Prior to the first flight, the modification team applied torque paint marks on the forward attachment bolt of the fin. This allowed the team to monitor the bolt after the three initial sorties to determine if it loosened from its original position. To mitigate fin failure due to structural fatigue, the team agreed that a careful external visual inspection of the ventral fin and access panel be performed after each flight where 0.9 Mach number or higher was reached. It was also necessary for the team to fly these missions over sparsely populated areas as much as practical.

In an actual event where the fin failed (which could be identified by the test conductor through our ground control rooms during flight), the test pilot would perform a controllability check, declare an in-flight emergency, and immediately return to base. The aircraft could still effectively be controlled with the loss of a ventral fin within the approved flight envelope. Of the two to three dozen instances where a single fin departed from the F-16 aircraft, there were no reported handling or stability problems related to those instances.

A safety review board convened to analyze the test team’s safety approach for the ALC flight test and concluded that our first sortie would be categorized as a ‘medium risk’ test flight. After that particular flight, the team would analyze the recorded parameters from the ALC ventral fin during flight, and compare the strain characteristics under the same flight conditions from the General Dynamics and Royal

Netherlands Air Force test. If the fin behaved as expected, the subsequent flights would be considered ‘low risk.’

5. ALC GROUND TESTS

Once the aircraft modifications were completed and passed the safety and electromagnetic interference inspections, the next step was to perform a functional ground test of the ALC components. Initially, the team confirmed that the DAS and telemetry systems on the aircraft were fully operational. This was accomplished simply by transmitting to the control room using the aircraft L-band telemetry system. While transmitting, the telemetry technicians and engineers fine-tuned the relevant aircraft, ALC fin, and LANTIRN-ALC pod parameters for proper real time display in the control rooms. A functionality check was successfully performed between the hand-held PC and the DBSJ actuators on the LANTIRN-ALC pod. A critical aspect of this specific test was to identify and confirm the optimum operating frequency of the DBSJ actuators.

As mentioned previously, the wind tunnel testing identified an optimal operating frequency of 830 Hz for the DBSJ actuators. During the functionality test, we used the hand-held PC to perform a frequency sweep between 800 to 900 Hz at 125 volts DC to confirm the optimal operating frequency of the DBSJ actuators. As predicted, the largest volumetric airflow from the DBSJ actuators occurred at or around 830 Hz, which became the baseline operating frequency for these test flights. The process for performing frequency sweeps prior to the sorties was formalized and standardized for future ALC test flights.

6. ALC FLIGHT TESTS

Test Objectives

A specific objective of our flight test was to characterize the flow field at which the LANTIRN-ALC pod wake interacted with the fin. The rationale behind this objective was to quantify the sensitivity of the fin in terms of aircraft attitude conditions, by defining where the pod wake interacted with the fin, and where it missed the fin altogether (the DBSJ actuators were not operated during these maneuvers). To satisfy this objective, the test pilot was required to maintain a constant target angle of attack, α , while slowly varying angle of sideslip, β , of the aircraft while at a constant altitude and airspeed. In the case of level α , the pilot executed a series of rudder sweeps to provide a range from -12 to +12 degrees β ⁵. Then, a series of rudder sweeps were executed to gather a full range of β during loaded wind-up turns in order to achieve and maintain a 2-degree-above level α condition. Finally, to achieve and maintain a 2-degree-below level α condition

⁵ After this particular sweep was performed on the first sortie, the pilot recommended limiting rudder inputs to set no more than 10 degrees β due to pilot-perceived reduction in directional stability above 12 degrees β .

while performing rudder sweeps, the pilot unloaded the aircraft during a slight climb (‘push over’ or ‘bunt’) using power and speed brake modulation as required to maintain test conditions. The combination of these maneuvers generated various responses on the ALC ventral fin, which was effectively recorded through the aircraft DAS system for analysis and will be used to later define the flow field created by the LANTIRN-ALC pod in relation to the ALC ventral fin.

Another specific objective of our flight test was to begin quantifying the effectiveness of the DBSJ actuators at various predefined flight conditions. Once on a specified test point, the pilot held conditions for roughly ten seconds allowing the DAS to record the ALC fin response generated by the pod without DBSJ actuation. The pilot maintained those conditions for another ten seconds while the flight test engineer in the rear cockpit activated the DBSJ actuators at 830 Hz (125 RMS volts), theoretically controlling the pod wake and reducing the overall pressure fluctuations on the ALC ventral fin. This concept of recording data with the DBSJ actuators on and off was applied to a number of flight test maneuvers ranging from 1-g cruise flight, level accelerations, and constant Mach number climbs or descents. In addition, the test pilot performed a combination of constant α and constant β maneuvers with the DBSJ actuators on and off. This was intended to quantify the DBSJ effectiveness relative to the aircraft attitude.

Figure 12 – ALC First Flight

Flight Test Overview

Testing was performed from 5,000 feet to 35,000 feet pressure altitude and from 0.4 to 0.9 Mach numbers. The highest test Mach number below 20,000 feet was 0.85, and our expected symmetric load factors range from 0 to 5 g's. This specific operating envelope satisfied the ALC safety requirements along with the ALC test objectives. The flight test team consisted of the test pilot and flight test engineer aboard the aircraft, and the test conductor operating from the TPS control room obtaining real time parameters via L-Band telemetry. Experts from AFRL, Lockheed Martin, and GE Global Research were also present in the control room to help analyze the real-time data.

The initial ALC flight tests consisted of only three flights, with roughly 1.5 hours in duration with no requirement for

in-flight refueling. Ideally, the team was interested in gathering as much data as possible, and prioritized the 1-g cruise flight data throughout the test envelope (especially the ‘corners’ of the envelope). As a result of the test point prioritization, the quantification of ventral fin sensitivity and DBSJ actuator effectiveness relative to the aircraft attitude was limited to a single Mach number and altitude condition, and a few combinations of α and β . Each test flight was designed with nearly identical profiles with the intent of duplicating test points with a variable change between each sortie.

The first sortie consisted of a ‘clean’ F-16 configuration, with the LANTIRN-ALC pod and the ALC ventral fin. After reviewing the initial fin response data from the first flight, the test team recognized the angle at which the DBSJ actuators were oriented on the pod was not opposite the fuselage. The decision was made to rotate the DBSJ extension can 45 degrees clockwise (looking aft) so the orifices were opposite the fuselage placing them more in line with the ventral fin for the second flight (also flown with a clean configuration). On the third flight, the team included 370-gallon wing tanks on the aircraft configuration, along with maintaining the DBSJ extension can orientation from the second flight. The test team concluded these initial sorties with a tremendous amount of data to be analyzed; all of it reflecting the first airborne demonstration of the ALC DBSJ. The primary goal of validating the A/C 453 ALC configuration as an effective evaluation platform for demonstrating the DBSJ actuators was met.

7. TEST RESULTS

The data from these initial ALC flight tests reflected the effectiveness of the DBSJ actuators when applied against the LANTIRN-ALC pod wake. In relation to the envelope tested, a reduction in the ALC ventral fin buffet environment due to the DBSJ actuators was observed at 0.5 Mach number 10,000 feet and at 0.5, 0.6 and 0.7 Mach numbers 5,000 feet for the ALC configuration without the wing tanks. The effects of the DBSJ actuators were mainly apparent in the frequency domain.

Power spectral density (PSD) data were generated from the time domain data using the Interactive Analysis and Display System (IADS) software. Each time domain record was divided into blocks of data using a 75-percent overlap technique. The size of the block was selected to provide a frequency resolution of approximately 1.3 Hz. A Hanning window was applied to each block prior to performing a Fast Fourier Transform on the block. The resulting transforms from all the blocks were averaged to yield the final frequency domain data.

A sample of the results (figure 13) show PSD data from the ALC ventral fin pressure transducers during the 1-g cruise test point at 0.5 Mach number, 10,000 feet. This particular

test point was from our second sortie (ALC configuration without wing tanks). Some of the dynamic load improvements from this sortie were attributed to an abrupt change in throttle position⁶ from 25 to 45 degrees at the same time the DBSJ actuators were turned on. Five out of the six pressure transducers showed a reduction in overall pressure when the DBSJ actuators were on. The ALC P3 fin measurement reflected increased pressure when the DBSJ actuators were on, however, the improvements at the other transducer locations resulted in an overall improvement across the ALC fin. The accelerometers and strain values, also reflecting improvement, are shown in figure 14. Figures 15 and 16 show PSD data from the ALC ventral fin parameters during the 1-g cruise test point at 0.5 Mach number 5,000 feet. This test point showed the DBSJ actuators made a positive improvement across all fin parameters. During this test point, there was no change in PLA when the DBSJ actuators were turned on. As a result, the improvements were attributed directly to the DBSJ actuation, which shows the system was effective in reducing the ventral fin buffet environment by manipulating the pod wake.

The DBSJ actuators also caused an increase in overall pressure across the ALC fin. In the third sortie, where the ALC configuration included external wing tanks, a subtle increase in the buffet environment was observed at 0.6 Mach number, 5,000 feet and at 0.7 Mach number, 10,000 feet when the DBSJ actuators were on. Figures 17 and 18 display the pressures, accelerations, and strain parameters respectively for the 0.7 Mach number, 10,000 feet condition. This phenomena deserves further investigation for future ALC flight tests.

For the ALC configuration without the wing tanks, the overall DBSJ actuator effectiveness in terms of 1- σ ratios at the different test conditions are shown in figure 19. The 1- σ values represent pressure fluctuations from 5 Hz to 1,000 Hz. The ratios are in terms of the DBSJ actuators ON to OFF. The pressure ratios from 0.95 and 1.05 indicated neither improvement nor worsening due to the DBSJ actuators. Pressure ratios below 0.95 indicated a decrease in pressure while ratios above 1.05 indicated an increase in pressure with the DBSJ actuators on. An increase in pressure did not necessarily imply a negative effect. Some of the values greater than 1.05 represented sensors that were either relatively quiet in comparison to other sensors during that test point, did not exhibit any significant differences in the frequency band of interest (100 to 300 Hz), or may have been particularly sensitive to engine inlet spillage and/or increased atmospheric turbulence at the 5,000-foot test points.

⁶ Small changes in throttle position, or power lever angle (PLA), caused sufficient changes in engine inlet spillage that altered the buffet flow field on the ALC fin. Therefore, it was necessary to ensure the test pilot did not adjust PLA as the DBSJ actuators are turned on.

Figure 13 – ALC Fin Pressures at 10,000 feet, 0.5 Mach Number, 1-g Cruise ALC Configuration Without Wing Tanks

Figure 14 – ALC Fin Accelerations and Strain at 10,000 feet, 0.5 Mach Number, 1-g Cruise ALC Configuration Without Wing Tanks

Figure 15 – ALC Fin Pressures at 5,000 feet, 0.5 Mach Number, 1-g Cruise ALC Configuration Without Wing Tanks

Figure 16 – ALC Fin Accelerations and Strain at 5,000 feet, 0.5 Mach Number, 1-g Cruise ALC Configuration Without Wing Tanks

Figure 17 – ALC Fin Pressures at 10,000 feet, 0.7 Mach Number, 1-g Cruise ALC Configuration With External Wing Tanks

Figure 18 – ALC Fin Accelerations and Strain at 10,000 feet, 0.7 Mach Number, 1-g Cruise ALC Configuration With External Wing Tanks

Figure 19 – DBSJ Actuator Effectiveness at Cruise ALC Configuration Without Wing Tanks

8. WAY AHEAD

The required ALC data were satisfactorily collected and recorded, and the data quality was good. Analysis of the test data was successful in identifying specific conditions under which future ALC testing should be performed.

Follow-on testing with the ALC configuration will be completed by student test pilots and student flight test engineers at the USAF TPS as part of their Test Management Projects (TMPs) which fulfills a requirement for graduation. The AFRL/TPS ALC program is a multiphase test program that will allow TPS students to perform flight test on other active flow control techniques. Follow-on phases plan to include an active structural control system, composed of materials with piezoelectric properties that changes shape and produces deformation in relation to input voltage.

This type of research involving student participation with TPS staff oversight to investigate new aerospace technologies in a cost-effective manner, is part of an ongoing transformation at the USAF Test Pilot School and

the Air Force Flight Test Center, a premier national test and evaluation asset for the aerospace community. The mission of the USAF Test Pilot School is to take the world’s best operational pilots and line engineers and teach them the prerequisite skills and knowledge to become the world’s best aerospace test and evaluation experts and future T&E leaders. USAF TPS TMPs not only provide the students with invaluable experience conducting real world aerospace research and/or T&E projects to “cut their teeth” on right before they graduate, it provides government and industry organizations with a method of collecting what is normally very expensive flight test data in a very cost effective manner. TPS pays for the flying hours and minor aircraft modification costs, the customer (government lab, AFIT, industry, etc.) provides the test article and funding for any major aircraft modifications, thus creating a win-win situation for all involved.

9. CONCLUSIONS

The successful execution of this initial ALC effort was a direct result of the creativity, dedication, and motivation of the participating team members. From the drawing board to the flights, and to the tremendous amount of time spent analyzing mounds of data, each person involved with the ALC program played a significant role in almost every aspect of the process.

In terms of satisfying our primary objective, the test team was successful in validating the ALC configuration as an effective platform for evaluating the use of the DBSJ actuator system. Specifically, we were able to quantify the buffet environment when the DBSJ actuators were on and off. We also identified that the DBSJ system affected the ventral fin buffet environment only between 0.5 and 0.7 Mach numbers, and was most effective in reducing the buffet environment at 0.5 Mach number, 5,000 feet. The technology is beginning to work as advertised, with further investigation on the way shortly.

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BIOGRAPHIES

Captain Raniel Hidalgo is currently the Chief of Airborne Instrumentation at the USAF Test Pilot School. He served as the TPS Project Manager and Flight Test Engineer for the ALC Program. Captain Hidalgo previously served as the Chief of Advanced Technology for the E-8C Joint Surveillance Target Attack Radar System, and Executive Officer for the E-10A Multi-Sensor

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Lieutenant Commander Gregory Burgess is the Staff Naval Exchange Officer and Technical Support Director for the USAF Test Pilot School. He is an Instructor Pilot in the F-16 and T-38 and is responsible for leading the Information Technology, Software Applications Development and Telemetry/Special Instrumentation Branches. He served as the Primary Test Pilot for the ALC Program.

Lieutenant Commander Burgess holds a B.S. in Aerospace and Ocean Engineering from Virginia Polytechnic Institute and State University, a command pilot with over 3,700 flying hours in over 40 different aircraft, and is a graduate of the U.S. Naval Test Pilot School (Class 109).

Mr. Reynaldo Enriquez is a graduate of the California State Polytechnic University in Pomona with a B.S. degree in Aerospace Engineering and an M.S. degree in Engineering with emphasis in Aeronautics. He served as the Structures Engineer, Test Conductor and Flight Test Engineer for the ALC program. He has

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Mr. John L. Minor is the Technical Director for the United States Air Force Test Pilot School and is President of the Society of Flight Test Engineers (SFTE). In his previous assignment he was the Master Instructor for the 412th Test Wing's Engineering Directorate Engineer Development Office.

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